

Effect of Sales Promotion Management on Organizational Profitability a Comparative Study of Cadbury Nig Plc and Nestle Nig Plc

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Abstract

This paper critically examined the impact of sales promotion and marketing on organizational profitability, with a specific focus on Cadbury Nig Plc and Nestlé Nig Plc, Lagos-State. This study employed a descriptive survey design. A sample size of 100 respondents was selected using convenient sampling technique of which 100 respondents filled and returned the questionnaire. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed using special software for statistics which is called statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20. The study found out that there was a significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability. Also, there is a significant relationship between consumers commitment and repeat purchase and therefore recommends that much bonuses should be in place to aid consumers to repeat purchase. Such bonuses include buying one get one free, coupon rate ticket among others.

Keywords: Sales Promotion, Consumer Commitment, Repeat Purchase, and Organizational Profitability.

Background to The Study

The basic objective of every firm is to increase the sale of goods as well as gaining high market share which leads to organizational profitability. Several approaches can be employed for the achievement of these goals; achieving these goals could be direct while others are indirect. Sales promotion is one of the approaches. Sales promotion is defined as a “diverse collection of incentive tools, mostly, a short term designed to stimulate quicker and/or greater purchase of particular products/services by consumers” (Kotler, 1998). Sales promotion is a strategical tool undertaken by organizations to promote and induce constant sales, usage or trial of a product or service (i.e initiations that are not covered by other elements of the marketing communication/promotional mix), the concept is termed strategical instruments because it is a direct method to gain customers and making them derive some satisfaction. It is an important component of an organization’s overall marketing strategy along with publicity or advertising, public relations, and personal selling (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2004). Sale promotion acts as a strategic competitive weapon or tools by providing an extra incentive for the target audience (known as customers) to purchase or support one brand over another. It is particularly effective in attracting, retaining of product trial and unplanned purchases (Aderemi, 2003).

Most marketers believe that a given product or service has a stable perceived price or value, and they use sales promotion to change this price value relationship by increasing the value and/or lowering the price compared with other components of the marketing mix (advertising, publicity, personal selling), it thus infer that among other promotional mix, sales promotion is the most prominent and costly one and this is because it stimulates prices and retain customers’ needs for a product. In determining the relative importance to rate sales promotion in the overall promotional mix, an organization should consider its finance and marketing budget as well as liquidity of the firm, the stage of the product in the life cycle, the nature of competition in the market, the target audience of the promotion, and the tangible and intangible nature of the product. For example, sales promotion is a particularly attractive alternative when the budget is surplus and favorable. In addition, sales promotion can be an effective tool in a highly competitive market, when the objective is to convince retailers to carry a new product or influence consumers to select it over those of competitors. More so, sales promotion tends to work best when it is applied to impulse products whose features can be judged at the point of purchase, rather than more complex, expensive items that might require hands on demonstration. Sales promotion includes communication activities that provide extra value or incentives to ultimate consumers, wholesalers, retailers or other organizational customers. It also stimulates sales, product trial (Kotler and Kelvin, 2006). The essence of this paper is to test the effect of sales promotion on organizational performance.

According to Kotler (2003), Sales Promotion is a key ingredient in marketing awareness and consists of a different collection of incentive tools, mostly short term designed to stimulate fast or greater purchase particular products or services by consumers. Sales promotions programmes are those activities other than stimulating consumer purchase or increasing sales. Sales promotion is one of the four aspects of the promotional mix. It is normally considered as a tool consisting of short-term incentives to encourage the purchase or sale of a product or service Examples of sales promotion

are found everywhere e.g. coupon rates, take one get one free, In the products view in the local supermarket that tempts impulse buyers with a wall of coke cartons, an executive who buys a new Compaq laptop computer gets a free carrying case. Sales promotion includes a wide variety of promotion tools designed to stimulate stronger market response (Kotler 2003)

Statement of Research Problems.

Bitta (2002) said that sales promotion plays a prominent role in strategic decisions which help in achieving the organizational objectives. It has been established in most studies that only consumers with repeat purchases are profitable (Nagar, 2009). It is not every repeat purchase of a customer that is connected to the consumer's patronage of a product. However, it is important to know that consumer's patronage is important for a repeat purchase. Therefore, marketers need to develop a marketing program that will not only reinforce customer's patronage but also stimulates repeat purchases. Therefore, the functions of sales promotion are not only to stimulate patronage of consumers but to encourage repeat purchase. Sales promotion has effects on various aspects of consumers purchase decisions such as brand choice, purchase time, quantity, and brand switching (Nijs, et al., 2001). Thus, sales promotion becomes an integral part of the marketing tactics for reaching the target market and it is the responsibility of marketers to combine elements of promotional strategies, which is promotional mix into coordinated plans of which sales promotion is part of. Sales promotions efforts are directed at final consumers and established to stimulate, influenced, and attract them of the goods and services receive that are offered.

Base on the above, the study sought to achieve the effect of sales promotion and marketing on organizational profitability with a study on Cadbury Nig PLC and Nestle Nig PLC.

Objectives of the Study.

The main purpose of this paper was to investigate the effect of sales promotion and marketing on organizational profitability. To achieve this purpose, the following set of specific objectives must be considered:

1. To know if there is a significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability.
2. To find out if there is any significant relationship between the consumer's commitment and repeat purchase of a product.

Research Questions.

To authenticate the above stated objectives, the following research questions must be asked and they include:

1. Is there a significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability?
2. Is there a significant relationship between a consumer's commitment and repeat purchase?

Research Hypotheses

The following are the hypothetical statement of the study and these are subject to statistical and data analysis, they include:

H01: There is no significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability.

H02: There is no significant relationship between the consumer's commitment and repeat purchase.

Scope and Limitation of the Study.

The scope cut across the following variables namely: sales promotion, consumer's commitment, organizational profitability, and repeat purchase. The relationship between these variables was tested and measured in two of the leading beverage manufacturing industries in Nigeria, namely Cadbury Nig PLC and Nestle Nig PLC. The basis for the adoption of these firms was champion by the fact that every manufacturing organization irrespective of the size engages in sales promotion and marketing activities, hence the need for the adoption of the firms.

Although business and other social sciences investigation strive to employ scientific tools and methods, even the very attempt is itself bedeviled by various kinds of problems: such problems limit the level of accuracy and reliability of the social scientist in any specific research endeavor.

Literature Review

Sales Promotion: Holistic View

Kotler (2001) describes sales promotion as an adverse collection of incentive tools, mostly short-term, designed to stimulate quicker and/or greater purchase of the particular brand, products, or service by consumers or the traders. He added that sales promotion had more impact at the mature stage of a product and that product managers might try to stimulate sales by modifying one or more marketing mix elements.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2002), consumer promotion is a category of sales promotion including free samples, winning contests, different price packs, and sweepstakes. Sales promotion is projected to increase the sales of the final ultimate consumers of the product. Some kinds of sales promotion are based on some sort of benefit whereas some are very communicative in type. (Kotler et al. 1999).

Blythe (2006) viewed sales promotion as any activity intended to generate a temporary boost in sales. This includes several communications activities pursued in an attempt to provide added value or incentives to consumers, wholesalers, retailers, or other organizational customers to stimulate immediate sales. Such efforts are usually geared towards stimulating product interest, trial, or purchase. It is specifically designed to boost quick sales and ultimately create loyalty.

Aham (2008) is of the opinion that sales promotion emerged as a reaction by manufacturers marketers, and marketing strategies like to find a short term solution to the problems of excess stock of goods which are available in variables manufacturers' warehouses but are not demanded by consumers and organization. Sales promotions are comparatively easy to apply and are likely to have an abrupt and considerable effect on the volume of sales (Hanssens et al, 2001).

The American Marketing Association (AMA) defined sales promotion as those marketing activities other than personal selling, advertising, publicity that stimulate consumer purchasing and dealer effectiveness such as display, shows and exhibitions, demonstrations and various non-recurrent selling efforts not in the ordinary routine. The development of the sales promotion strategies requires that a firm must determine what its best potential markets are and then select the means by which it will try to sell it to its customers. George (1998) posits that sales promotion is a direct inducement that offers an extra value or incentive for the product to the sales force, distributors or the ultimate consumer with the primary objective of creating an immediate sale.

Sales promotions can be categorized into three depending on the initiator and the target of the market. These include:

- **Consumer promotions**

Consumer promotions are those efforts/tools aimed at influencing the trial consumer (Bamiduro, 2001). They are promotions offered by manufacturers directly to consumers (Blattberg and Neslin, 1990). Such promotions are designed to encourage consumers to immediate (or nearly immediate) action thereby creating a form of impulse buying (Courtland and John, 1992). Consumer's promotion techniques can be used to attract people into a particular store, to induce new product or to promote established products. To accomplish this task, markets have developed quite a variety of sales promotion techniques or tools.

- **Retailer promotions**

Retailer promotions are promotions offered by retailers to consumers. These include allowances and discounts, factory-sponsored in-store demonstration, trade shows, sales contests, cooperative advertising, etc.

- **Trade promotions**

Trade promotions are promotions offered by manufacturers to retailers or other trade entities (Blattberg and Neslin, 1990). They are the aspect where the manufacturer is concerned not only with promoting the product to the consumers but also with whether the product is on the retailers' shelves when the customers go to the store to buy (Osuala, 1998). Retailer promotion and consumer promotion are directed toward the consumers by retailers and manufacturers, respectively. The manufacturer's direct trade promotion to the retailers.

Sales Promotion and Marketing Strategies

- **Push strategy:**

As the name applies, it indicates the necessary transfer of goods through marketing channels. push strategy involves convincing trade intermediary channel members to "push" the product through the distribution channels to the final consumer through promotions and personal selling efforts (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007). The company promotes the product through a reseller who in turn promotes it to yet another reseller or the final consumer the push strategy is more or like using an issue house to reach the final consumers. Trade- promotion objectives are to persuade retailers or wholesalers to carry a brand, give a brand shelf space, promote a brand in advertising, and/or push a brand to final consumers. Typical tactics employed in the push strategy are allowances, buy-back guarantees, free trials, contests, specialty advertising items, discounts, displays, and premiums.

- **Pull strategy**

This is the direct opposites of the push strategy, while push is from manufacturer to customers pull is the desire of products by the customers which are from the manufacturer, pull strategy also attempts to get consumers to "pull" the product from the manufacturer through the marketing channel. The company focuses its marketing communications efforts on consumers in the hope that it stimulates interest and demand for the product at the end-user level. This strategy is often employed if distributors are reluctant to carry a product because it gets as many consumers as possible to go to retail outlets and request the product, thus pulling it through the channel (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007). Consumer-promotion objectives are to entice consumers to try a new product, lure customers away from competitors' products, get consumers to "load up" on a mature product, hold & reward loyal customers, and build consumer relationships Typical tactics employed in the pull strategy are: samples, coupons, cash refunds and rebates, premiums, advertising specialties, loyalty programs/patronage rewards, contests, sweepstakes, games, and point-of-purchase (POP) displays.

- **Combination strategy**

This strategy requires both of the above strategies working together. The "push" is used to get more products into the hands of retailers and wholesalers while advertising and product tie-ins with other products are used as a "pull" to get more people to want to buy the product (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007).

Effect of Sales Promotion on Organizational Performance

The effect that sales promotions have on the organizational performance are:

1. Encouraging the purchase of large size unit. Sales promotion consists of a diverse collection of incentive tools, a mostly short term designed to stimulate the quicker or greater purchase of products or service by consumer e.g. The use of premiums, product warranties, etc. stimulate consumer purchase in larger quantities, Rotimosho (2003)
2. Generating trials among non-users. Trials among non-users of a product are generated through the invitation of prospective purchasers to try the product without cost or little cost with the hope that they will buy the product.
3. Persuading retailers to carry new items and a higher level of inventory. Sales promotion encourages retailers to give shelf space to new products. Manufacturers provide retailers with financial incentives to stock new products.
4. Encouraging off season buying. Sales promotion has also encouraged off season buying especially during the festive periods, people tend to buy more of a particular product because of the added value, compared to a normal season.

5. Building brand loyalty. Sales promotion helps to build brand loyalty by giving the seller the opportunity to attract a loyal and profitable set of customers which provides sellers some protections from the competition and greater control in planning their marketing mix. Shira (2003)

Conclusively, sales promotion has been seen to focus on customer relationship management, free gifts, free sample, price discount, etc. If an organization effectively implements sales promotion techniques, it will not only encourage large purchase but it will also increase the sales performance of an organization, invariably leading to the achievement of the stated objectives.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

For the purpose of this study, the pull and push theory to marketing and sales promotion were considered: and these theories are explained below:

Pull Theory

Pull Theory is about trying to distribute products directly to customers to increase their demand for the product. Advertising and tie-ins with other products or services are the keys to this strategy. The ideology behind this theory stipulates that if you increase the demand for your product by consumers, they will in turn demand the product from retailers, retailers will demand more of the product from wholesalers and wholesalers will demand more products from the manufacturer, this theory can be best explained as Distribution Channel theory, where products are not complete until it gets to the final consumers. This is a way to increase sales without decreasing the sale value of the merchandise.

Push Theory Using the Push Theory, one can increase sales by creating incentives to wholesalers or retailers to sell more of the product. In this method, marketers would offer discounts to wholesalers or retailers who buy the product in bulk. This leaves them with more of your merchandise on hand and drives them to sell more of your product. Giving them the discount "pushes" them to buy more of your product at a lower price to increase the amount of money they make. In turn, they must "push" your products to customers because they will make a better return on them than on similar products supplied to them by your competitors.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design was used in this study. The target population of this study comprises of the general staff of Cadbury Nigeria Plc and Nestle Nig Plc. Thus, Role of marketing and sales promotion on firm profitability and its application are relevant at this level prompting the choice of the population. However, a sample size of 100 was determined using the convenience sampling technique. This study is expected to produce both quantitative and qualitative data. Once the questionnaires are received, they were coded and edited for completeness and consistency. Quantitative data was analyzed by employing descriptive statistics and inferential analysis using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20. This technique gives simple summaries about the sample data and present quantitative descriptions in a manageable form, Gupta (2004). Together with simple graphics analysis, descriptive statistics form the basis of virtually every quantitative analysis to data, Kothari (2004). The significance testing was done at 5% level of significance and SPSS was used for this purpose. The data was then presented using frequency distribution tables, bar charts and pie charts for easier understanding

FINDINGS.

A total of 100 Questionnaires (representing 100%) were distributed, in which 100 was returned, a percentage of which is 100%. However, the returned Questionnaires are however shown below:

Sales Promotion is a tool for organizational growth

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
Agreed	55	55.0	55.0	75.0
Undecided	15	15.0	15.0	90.0
Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	95.0
Strongly Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 20% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion is a tool for organizational growth, 55% of the respondents Agreed to the contrary, 15% of the respondents were unsure, finally 5% of the respondents disagreed and 5% of the respondents strongly disagreed that Sales Promotion is a tool for organizational growth. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion is a tool for organizational growth.

Sales Promotion is a viable marketing strategy used by marketers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	11	11.0	11.0	11.0
Agreed	49	49.0	49.0	60.0
Undecided	20	20.0	20.0	80.0
Disagreed	15	15.0	15.0	95.0
Strongly Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 11% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion is a viable marketing strategy used by marketers, 49% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 20% of the respondents were unsure, 15% of the respondents disagreed and 5% of the respondents strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion is a viable marketing strategy used by marketers.

Sales Promotion influences customers demand

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
Agreed	40	40.0	40.0	50.0
Undecided	10	10.0	10.0	60.0
Disagreed	35	35.0	35.0	95.0
Strongly Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 10% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion influences customers demand, 40% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 10% of the respondents were unsure, 35% of the respondents disagreed and 5% of the respondents strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion influences customers demand.

Sales Promotion has a relationship with organizational profitability

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	35	35.0	35.0	35.0
Agreed	35	35.0	35.0	70.0
Undecided	15	15.0	15.0	85.0
Disagreed	10	10.0	10.0	95.0
Strongly Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 35% of the respondents strongly agreed that basic Sales Promotion has a relationship with organizational profitability, 35% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 15% of the respondents were unsure, 10% of the respondents disagreed and 5% of the respondents strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents strongly agreed as well as agreed that Sales Promotion has a relationship with organizational profitability.

Sales Promotion involves extra bonus given to customers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	16	16.0	16.0	16.0
Agreed	73	73.0	73.0	89.0
Disagreed	6	6.0	6.0	95.0
Strongly Disagreed	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 16% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion involves extra bonus given to customers, 73% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 6% of the respondents disagreed and 5% of the respondents strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion involves extra bonus given to customers.

Sales promotion should be given allocation in an organization

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
Agreed	45	45.0	45.0	75.0
Undecided	19	19.0	19.0	94.0
Disagreed	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales promotion should be given allocation in an organization, 45% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 19% of the respondents were unsure, 6% of the respondents disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales promotion should be given allocation in an organization.

Sales Promotion should be given many funds so as to make it functional

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
Agreed	49	49.0	49.0	79.0
Undecided	15	15.0	15.0	94.0
Disagreed	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion should be given many funds so as to make it functionate, 49% of the respondents agreed to the contrary, 15% of the respondents were unsure, 6% of the respondents disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion should be given many funds so as to make it functionate.

Sales Promotion influences repeat purchase

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agreed	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
Agreed	43	43.0	43.0	73.0
Undecided	11	11.0	11.0	84.0
Disagreed	6	6.0	6.0	90.0
Strongly Disagreed	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

The table above shows that 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that Sales Promotion influences repeat purchase, 11% of the respondents were unsure, 6% of the respondents disagreed and 10% of the respondents strongly disagreed. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that Sales Promotion influences repeat purchase.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

The Pearson correlation (r) was employed to test the association between the variables stated in the hypotheses at 0.01 level of significance.

Decision Rule: Accept the Alternative Hypotheses and reject the Null Hypotheses if the Pearson correlation (r) is positive. The level of strength between this variable can also be determined as indicated in a table below:

Coefficient Value	Strength of Association
0.1 < /r / < .3	Small correlation
0.3 < /r / < .5	Medium/moderate correlation
/r / > .5	Large/strong correlation

Where r means the absolute value of the Pearson correlation coefficient.

HYPOTHESIS ONE

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability.

Correlations

		Sales Promotion	Organizational Profitability
Sales Promotion	Pearson Correlation	1	.640**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Organizational Profitability	Pearson Correlation	.640**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

From the table above, the Pearson correlation (r) analysis between Sales Promotion and Organizational variables is 0.640, indicating a strong positive correlation between Sales Promotion and Organizational Profitability of workers variables. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability.

HYPOTHESIS TWO

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the consumer's commitment and repeat purchase.

Correlations

		Consumer's Commitment	Repeat Purchase
Consumer's Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.244*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.014
	N	100	100
Repeat Purchase	Pearson Correlation	.244*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	
	N	100	100

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher Fieldwork (2018).

From the table above, the Pearson correlation (r) analysis between consumer commitment and repeat purchase variables is 0.244, indicating a small positive correlation between consumer commitment and repeat purchase variables. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between consumers commitment and repeat purchase.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATION.

The study was aimed at investigating the impact of sales promotion on organizational profitability. The first finding of the study shows that there was a significant relationship between sales promotion and organizational profitability. This implies that when there is a sale promotion in place, there tends to be a positive increase in organizational profitability and vice versa. Sales promotion are extra benefit consumers get after a certain rate and quantity has been bought, thus when these quantities are bought, the organization, in turn, gives extra benefit such as the extra quantity of product, coupon rate. This singular action, therefore, spices up the intention of customers to purchase a product and this, in turn, increase organizational profitability.

Finally, the study finds out that there is a significant relationship between consumers commitment and repeat purchase. This implies that when the consumer is being committed to a particular product, there tends to repeat purchase from such a consumer. This is common within high prestige and quality product. When a product is of good quality and standard, consumers tend to be committed therefore repeat purchase of such a product is created.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommended tips to aid in sales promotion of an organization as well as increased organizational profitability:

1. Many bonuses should be in place to aid consumers repeat purchase. Such bonuses include buying one get one free, coupon rate ticket among others.
2. The organization should inculcate the habit of personal selling so as to encourage repeat purchase and organizational profitability.
3. The organization should produce quality and standardize product so as to encourage repeat purchase from consumer.

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